

MANAGING LOWER URINARY TRACT SYMPTOMS AFTER PROSTATE SURGERY WITH HOMOEOPATHY: A CASE REPORT

Dr. Rashmi Rajendra More Assistant Professor, Department of Homoeopathic Repertory and Case Taking, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College, Pune.

Abstract

Background:

Lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) significantly impact quality of life, particularly in older men. The International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS), including a quality-of-life question, is a standard tool for symptom assessment. This case report highlights the role of individualized homoeopathic treatment in managing persistent LUTS post-transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP).

Methods: A post-TURP patient with persistent LUTS was evaluated using the IPSS scale at baseline. Homoeopathic treatment was prescribed based on individualized symptoms, with monthly follow-ups and IPSS reassessments every three months over one year.

Results: The patient showed significant improvement in LUTS, with a marked reduction in IPSS scores and enhanced quality of life. Symptoms such as urgency, nocturia, and frequency were effectively managed, with sustained improvement over follow-up.

Conclusion: Individualized homoeopathic treatment effectively managed persistent LUTS in a post-TURP patient, addressing both physical and psychological aspects, and improving overall outcomes.

Keywords: LUTS, IPSS, post-TURP, homoeopathy, quality of life.

Introduction:

Lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) refer to a group of medical symptoms involving dysfunctional urinary voiding, categorized into irritative symptoms (urinary frequency, urgency, dysuria, and nocturia) and obstructive symptoms (hesitancy, poor stream, post-void dribbling, and overflow incontinence).^[1,2,3] These symptoms are prevalent in the elderly population, with their prevalence and severity increasing with age, particularly after 50 years.^[4] By age 90, LUTS affects up to 90% of men, significantly impacting physical and mental well-being.^[5]

LUTS may lead to reduced quality of life, with affected individuals avoiding social settings and struggling to complete tasks at home or work^[6]. The severity of symptoms varies depending on etiological and lifestyle factors, influencing health-related quality of life (HRQOL) and contributing to high healthcare costs. Additionally, LUTS can persist or recur even in patients who have undergone operative procedures for prostate conditions, such as benign prostatic hyperplasia.

The homeopathic approach to managing LUTS focuses on individualized treatment, considering both physical and mental symptoms to address the root cause of the condition. By recognizing the multifactorial nature of LUTS, homeopathy aims to provide early intervention, prevent progression, and enhance the quality of life in affected individuals.

The International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) is a standardized tool used to assess the severity of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) in men. It evaluates symptoms such as frequency, urgency, and nocturia through seven questions and includes one additional question to assess the impact of symptoms on quality of life (QOL).

This case report presents a patient with LUTS following transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP), assessed using the International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS) at baseline. Symptom severity and clinical progress were systematically evaluated during subsequent follow-up visits.

Case report:

A 70-year-old retired male with a history of diabetes mellitus and hypertension for 10 years on regular treatment presented on 14/08/2020 with urinary complaints for the past 4 months, including increased frequency of micturition³⁺, hesitancy³⁺, weak urinary stream²⁺ and nocturia²⁺ occurring 3–4 times per night. The symptoms, which initially improved after a TURP procedure in November 2019 for benign prostatic hyperplasia, recurred after 6–7 months and have gradually progressed. Despite having the urge to urinate, he experiences delays in voiding and wishes to avoid further surgical intervention.

Past History

- Diabetes mellitus and hypertension for 10 years
- Status post-TURP and bladder neck incision (2019)

Associated Complaints: Chronic constipation ²⁺, requiring daily laxatives post-surgery

Personal history:

- Appetite – Normal. Desires – sweets³⁺
- Micturition : Hesitancy – has to wait longer to void urine inspite of having the urge³⁺
 - Frequency – increased 7-8 times/day³⁺
 - Weak stream – yes²⁺
 - Straining to urinate – no straining
 - Post micturition dribbling – no
 - Urgency – no urgency
 - Nocturia – 3-4 times/night²⁺
- Sleep – disturbed due to complaints
- Thermal – Chilly
- Mind – The patient exhibits a controlling and obstinate nature, expecting others to follow his instructions²⁺. He gets angry when contradicted³⁺ and is easily offended²⁺. He is highly protective of his family, worries excessively about their well-being, and fears potential future hardships, particularly financial³⁺. He is meticulous about money and avoids unnecessary expenses. He tends to perform tasks hurriedly²⁺, showing signs of impatience and anxiety.

General Examination:

- Height: 5'6"
- Weight: 75 kg
- BP: 140/100 mmHg

Investigations:

- USG A+P : Prostatomegaly with median lobe indenting the bladder base, volume – 55cc with significant post-void residue (Prevoid – 450cc, postvoid – 170cc), mild splenomegaly, cholelithiasis, fatty infiltration in the liver
- Histopathology: Benign prostatic hyperplasia

Final Diagnosis: Lower urinary tract symptoms in K/C/O diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and benign prostatic hyperplasia (post-TURP status).

Table 1: Analysis and Evaluation of symptoms

Analysis of symptoms	Evaluation
Mental generals-	1. Gets angry when contradicted ³⁺
1. Gets angry when contradicted ³⁺	2. Thinks about money all the time, money-minded nature ³⁺
2. Thinks about money all the time, money-minded nature ³⁺	3. Concerned about his family ²⁺
3. Concerned about his family ²⁺	4. Things should be done as told by him, tells everyone what is to be done ²⁺
4. Things should be done as told by him, tells everyone what is to be done ²⁺	5. Fears about poverty in future ²⁺
5. Fears about poverty in future ²⁺	6. Superior and everyone should listen to him ²⁺
6. Superior and everyone should listen to him ²⁺	7. Obstinate nature ²⁺
7. Obstinate nature ²⁺	8. Gets offended easily ²⁺
8. Gets offended easily ²⁺	9. Does everything in hurry ²⁺
9. Does everything in hurry ²⁺	10. Fears if something happen in future ¹⁺
10. Fears if something happen in future ¹⁺	11. Desire – sweets ³⁺
Physical generals-	12. Increased frequency of micturition ³⁺
1. Desire – sweets ³⁺	13. Hesitancy present ³⁺
2. Chilly patient	14. Weak urinary stream ²⁺
Physical particulars-	15. Nocturia ²⁺
1. Increased frequency of micturition ³⁺	16. Constipation ²⁺
2. Hesitancy present ³⁺	17. Chilly patient
3. Weak urinary stream ²⁺	
4. Nocturia ²⁺	
5. Constipation ²⁺	

Repertory sheet:

	I/c	sulph.	nux-v.	puls.	sep.	merc	phos.	caust.	calc.	sil.	ars.	nit-a-c	petr.	staph.	thui.	me
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
	32	32	32	31	31	31	29	29	29	29	29	29	28	28	28	28
	84	70	59	57	66	62	40	59	58	57	51	47	39	49	47	46
1. MIND - ANGER - contradiction; from (51) 3	■															
2. MIND - AVARICE (41) 3	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
3. MIND - ANXIETY - family; about his (29) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
4. MIND - DICTATORIAL (50) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
5. MIND - FEAR - poverty, of (38) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
6. MIND - HAUGHTY (77) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
7. MIND - OBSTINATE (142) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
8. MIND - OFFENDED, easily (119) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
9. MIND - HURRY (173) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
10. MIND - FEAR - happen, something will (107) 1	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
11. GENERALS - FOOD and DRINKS - sweets - desire (198) 3	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
12. BLADDER - URINATION - frequent (286) 3	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
13. BLADDER - URINATION - retarded, must wait for urine to start (85) 3	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
14. BLADDER - URINATION - feeble stream (85) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
15. BLADDER - URINATION - frequent - night (162) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■
16. RECTUM - CONSTIPATION (403) 2	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■	■

Prescription: Lycopodium 200

Assessment:The IPSS instrument was utilized to assess the severity of the patient’s lower urinary tract symptoms. His pre-inclusion IPSS score of 15 indicated moderate LUTS severity. The findings aligned with the clinical diagnosis of LUTS associated with benign prostatic hyperplasia. The patient was monitored with monthly follow-up visits, and IPSS assessments were conducted every three months to evaluate symptom progression and treatment outcomes.

Table 2: Follow-up & Intervention:

Month	Observations	Intervention
1 st	Constipation reduced, takes laxative once 3-4 days Nocturnal frequency 2-3 times	Lycopodium 200/3 doses
2 nd	Constipation reduced, laxatives once a week. Frequency reduced, 6-7 times.	Lycopodium 200/3 doses
3 rd	No much difference, status quo IPSS score – 13	Lycopodium 200/3 doses
4 th	Frequency better Hesitancy reduced Urinary flow improving	Sac Lac
5 th	No urgency, urinary flow better Nocturnal frequency 1-2 times	Sac Lac
6 th	Frequency 5-6 times No urgency, hesitancy much better IPSS score – 10	Lycopodium 200/3 doses
7 th	Patient much better	Sac Lac
8 th	Hesitancy present with incomplete sensation No urgency	Lycopodium 200/3 doses
9 th	Passing normal stools, flatus. Frequency 4-5 times Urinary flow improved IPSS score – 8	Sac Lac
10 th	Overall better	Sac Lac
11 th	Urgency much reduced Incomplete voiding sensation & hesitancy occasionally	Lycopodium 200/3 doses
12 th	Patient improved IPSS score - 7	Sac Lac

Table 3: Change in symptom domains of IPSS at baseline, after 6 months and after 1 year

IPSS Parameters	Pre-inclusion	After 6 months	After 1 year
1.Incomplete Emptying	2	1	1
2.Frequency	4	3	2
3.Intermittency	0	0	0
4.Urgency	1	1	0
5.Weak Stream	4	3	2
6.Nocturia	4	2	2
Total	15	10	7
Quality of Life Due to Urinary Symptoms	Mostly Dissatisfied	Mixed	Mostly Satisfied

Discussion:

Lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) are common in older patients, especially after procedures like transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP). These symptoms, which include urinary urgency, frequency, and nocturia, can significantly affect quality of life. The IPSS scale is widely used to assess the severity of LUTS and includes a quality of life question for comprehensive evaluation. In this case, a post-TURP patient with moderate LUTS was treated with individualized homoeopathic remedies. Over a one-year period, the patient showed significant improvement in symptoms, as reflected by a reduction in the IPSS score. This suggests that homoeopathy can be an effective treatment for managing LUTS, especially in cases where conventional treatments offer limited relief.

Conclusion:

This case highlights the potential of homoeopathy in managing LUTS, particularly post-TURP, with significant symptom relief and improved quality of life. Further research is needed to confirm these findings, but this case supports the use of homoeopathic treatments as a viable option for LUTS management.

Financial support and sponsorship:

Nil.

Conflicts of interest:

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

References:

1. *Société Internationale d'Urologie*. (n.d.). <https://www.siu-urology.org>
2. *Urinary problems (LUTS)*. (n.d.). Healthy Male. <https://www.healthymale.org.au/mens-health/urinary-problems-luts#anchor-303>
3. LUTS, Department of Urology, NHS Trust.
4. Lower Urinary Tract Conditions in Elderly Patients, Geriatric Nephrology Curriculum, American Society of Nephrology
5. Mehra, P., Roja, V., Sharma, B., Oberai, P., Reddy, G. R. C., Arya, D., RajaKumar, B. S. J., Mohanan, P., Prusty, A., Padmanabhan, M., & Manchanda, R.(2018). Homoeopathic treatment for lower urinary tract symptoms in men with benign prostatic hyperplasia: An open label randomised multicentric placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Indian Journal of Research in Homoeopathy*, 12(3), 113. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijrh.ijrh_36_18
6. Guidelines on Male Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms (LUTS), including Benign Prostatic Obstruction; EAU Pocket Guidelines 2012. https://uroweb.org/wpcontent/uploads/11_Male_LUTS.pdf
7. Schroyens, F. (2004, January 1). *Synthesis*.
8. RADAR (Rapid Aid to Drug Aimed Research) Software.